

THE GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK IN GENERAL

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Abstract: This article analyzes structural discrepancies between English and Uzbek by presenting concrete examples of their differences and similarities.

Key words: Verbs, suffixes, order, numerals, grammatical transformations, syntactical structures, tenses.

We are already aware that declarative statements in English have the following structure: Subject – Predicate – Object. Uzbek sentences are produced according to another scheme: Subject, object, and predicate (at the end of a phrase). As a result, the word order in English and Uzbek phrases differs significantly. Furthermore, suffixes like -ni and -ini are commonly employed in Uzbek phrases. Three types of structural discordances between English and Uzbek set expressions can be identified: 1. Complete conformance. 2. Partial conformance. 3. Total discordance.

The term «**complete structural concordance**» refers to the alignment of structures, word combinations, and parts of speech between English and Uzbek. Consider the number category, which is common in both languages:

I have seen the movie-Men kino ko'rdim

I have seen the movies-Men kinolar ko'rdim

Let me introduce my friend – Do'stimni tanishtirishga ijozat bering.

Let me introduce my friends – Do'stlarimni tanishtirishga ijozat bering.

However, the word order in these phrases differs: in English, the predicate comes after the subject, whereas in Uzbek, the predicate comes after both the subject and the object. There are very few fundamentally equivalent English and Uzbek speech formulations. Typically, such expressions include two or three parts: an international telegraph, xalqaro telegramma travelers' check - Sayohatchilar cheki Categories that are partially discordant include tense, voice, and case. There are two cases in English and six in Uzbek. I've heard a lot about your country, Sizing

mamlakatingiz to'g'risida ko'p eshitganman. Two English words—your country—are translated by one Uzbek word—mamlakatingiz. Furthermore, they vary in terms of case categorization. Another example: We are from Tashkent (Biz Toshkentdanmiz). Three English lexemes from Tashkent are blended into a single Uzbek lexeme, Toshkentdanmiz.

As we can see, English phrases consist of a numeral and a noun (singular and plural), but Uzbek phrases consist of a numeral and a noun in the singular. Even in circumstances of complete semantic agreement, there may be exposed cases of partial structural discordance: a list of items - molar royhati (word order differs+Uzbek suffix —il in the term —ro'yxati) customs limitations - bojxona cheklovlari (same word order, but with the Uzbek suffix —il) import license - import uchun ruhsatnoma (same word order with the Uzbek postposition —uchuni).

Total structural discordance is most evident in the category of possession, which is expressed by possessive suffixes in Uzbek and possessive pronouns in English

Possessive pronouns in English:

Can I introduce you to my family?

Sizni oilam bilan tanishtirsam bo'ladimi?

This is your invitation, please.

Marhamat, sizning taklifnomangiz

So, based on these common examples, we can conclude that a communicant in English-Uzbek communication should be familiar with all English possessive pronouns as well as Uzbek possessive suffixes. Total grammatical discordance is also evident in the use of English articles, which do not exist in the Uzbek language system but can sometimes be represented via another lexical means:

I'd like to present you with this gift - Men sizga mana bu sovg'ani topshirmoqchi edim.

The Uzbek demonstrative pronouns (mana bu) translate the English definite article—the.

Such a great surprise! - Qanday ajoyib uchrashuv!

In this Uzbek set statement, the English article (a) is not rendered.

The most vivid examples of total structural discordances can be presented on the basis of English and Uzbek set expressions in the form of sentences:

I should appreciate you - Sizga minnatdorchilik bildirishim kerak.

I am deeply sorry - Meni afv eting.

It is simply the opposite way around - Aksincha. As the examples indicate, the meaning and communicative objective of informing or presenting particular information, desire, point of view, or attitude toward something is identical in both languages, but their grammatical forms are completely different.

Result and Discussion to translate the semantic content of speech formulas from one language to another, we use a variety of grammatical transformations such as word order shift, removing some words, adding words, part of speech conversion, and others. One of the most common types of grammatical transformation is a change in word order, or the position of components of speech. Please accept my heartfelt greetings for your birthday- Tug'ilgan kuningizda mening samimiy tilaklarimni qabul qiling. In these cases, we see a change in structure: in the English form, the cause for congratulation appears in the second part of the sentence, whereas in the Uzbek sentence, the reason appears at the beginning of the sentence. Furthermore, the English word "please" is eliminated in Uzbek since its meaning is conveyed by other sentence components. Another example of changing word order: *I wish you speedy recovery - Tezda sog'ayib ketishingizni tilayman.*

In these examples, we see a change in word order as well as a conversion of parts of speech: in English, the phrase «speedy recovery» is indicated by adjective + noun, whereas in Uzbek, «tezda sog'ayib ketishingizni» is expressed by adverb + verb. He is an excellent speaker, U yahshi gapiradi. As it is clear, English - good speaker is expressed by an adjective + noun, in Uzbek we have —yaxshi gapiradi – adverb + verb.

After a thorough examination of the causes of entire structural discordances between English and Uzbek phrases, we identified the most common ones:

1. There is no comparable construction to render in another language.
2. Word combinations in both languages have unique characteristics related to lexical meaning and grammatical forms.
3. The absence of the same part of speech as this meaningful content (English articles and —that!) necessitates translating it with another part of speech. English articles transmit a variety of information, including skepticism, indexing, numbering, and emphasis.

When articles are used in English sentences, their meaning is reproduced using various language meanings in Uzbek: When we got at the airport, Mr. Brown had informed us that you would not be coming. – Biz aeroportga kelganimida qandaydir janob Braun siz kelmasligingizni aytdi. The Uzbek indefinite pronoun - qandaydir (someone) transfers the English article (a).

Inversion is at the root of many structural discordances. It is natural because English sentences are based on the Subject + Predicate structure. In Uzbek sentences, the predicate is placed at the end:

I beg your pardon – Sizdan uzr so'rayman.

I can't agree with you – Fikringizga qo'shila olmayman.

If you want to know my opinion – Mening fikrimni bilmoqchi bo'lsangiz.

In some English-Uzbek sentences, parts of speech are inverted. Diplomatic activity has increased significantly during the last week. (O'tgan haftada diplomatic munosabatlarning faollashuvi kuzatildi). English —last weekl is used as the subject of the sentence, but in the Uzbek sentence —o'tgan haftadal is adverbial modifier of place.

Another challenge in English-Uzbek speech is expressing gender using pronouns like —he,-she,-his,-herl, and -him in English. In Uzbek, the pronoun system does not include those that can express gender:

She is from England – U (kishi) Angliyadan.

He is from Switzerland – U (kishi) Shveysariyadan.

As the examples demonstrate, there is no rigid gender indexing in Uzbek phrases (as in English), and the same pronoun can be used for both males and females. Structural discordance can occur when rendering elaborate and complex sentences. In another language, the position of the main and subordinate clauses can be modified:

I remember the time when we were children. – Men bolalik chog'imizni eslayman.

The complex sentence in English is translated into a simple sentence in Uzbek because the subordinate clause in the English sentence becomes an adjective + object phrase in Uzbek.

Uzbek people often ask about someone's health: Sogligingiz yashimi? (Is your health good? Is your health in a good condition?). But English people usually use one common and frequent question - How are you? In speech formulas of request the verb appears at the beginning in English sentences, as for Uzbek - at the end + negative form is used for producing polite request:

Would you give me your book? - Kitobingizni berib turolmaysizmi?

Could you stay here another day? - Bu erda yana bir kun qololmaysizmi?

Conclusion. As shown in the instances above, politeness is expressed in English by the verbs —couldl, —wouldl, etc., and in Uzbek by negative verbs: —yordam qilolmaysizmi, —turolmaysizmi,etc. These are also clear examples of structural discordance between English and Uzbek set phrases. As a result, the

grammatical system of any language is extremely important to its operation. To produce relevant meaningful information in a correct grammatical construction, one must have complete understanding of both languages and comprehend their grammatical quirks. The most challenging issues in this aspect include syntactical structures, pronouns, articles, gender, tenses, and other grammatical categories.

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